

SOME REMARKS CONCERNING THE DISTRIBUTION OF THE SMARANDACHE FUNCTION

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The Smarandache function is a numerical function $S: \mathbb{N}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{N}^*$ $S(k)$ representing the smallest natural number n such that $n!$ is divisible by k . From the definition it results that $S(1)=1$.

I will refer for the beginning the following problem:

"Let k be a rational number, $0 < k \leq 1$. Does the diophantine equation $\frac{S(n)}{n} = k$ has always solutions? Find all k such that the equation has an infinite number of solutions in \mathbb{N}^* " from "Smarandache Function Journal".

I intend to prove that equation hasn't always solutions and case that there are an infinite number of solutions is when $k = \frac{1}{r}$, $r \in \mathbb{N}^*$, $k \in \mathbb{Q}$ and $0 < k \leq 1 \Rightarrow$ there are two relatively prime non negative integers p and q such that $k = \frac{q}{p}$, $p, q \in \mathbb{N}^*$, $0 < q \leq p$. Let n be a solution of the equation $\frac{S(n)}{n} = k$. Then $\frac{S(n)}{n} = \frac{p}{q}$, (1). Let d be a highest common divisor of n and $S(n)$: $d = (n, S(n))$. The fact that p and q are relatively prime and (1) implies that $S(n) = qd$, $n = pd \Rightarrow S(pd) = qd$ (*).

This equality gives us the following result: $(qd)!$ is divisible by $pd \Rightarrow [(qd - 1)! \cdot q]$ is divisible by p . But p and q are relatively prime integers, so $(qd-1)!$ is divisible by p . Then $S(p) \leq qd - 1$.

I prove that $S(p) \geq (q - 1)d$.

If we suppose against all reason that $S(p) < (q - 1)d$, it means $[(q - 1)d - 1]!$ is divisible by p . Then $(pd) \mid [(q - 1)d]!$ because $d \mid (q - 1)d$, so $S(pd) \leq (q - 1)d$. This is contradiction with the fact that $S(pd) = qd > (q - 1)d$. We have the following inequalities:

$$(q - 1)d \leq S(p) \leq qd - 1.$$

For $q \geq 2$ we have from the first inequality $d \leq \frac{S(p)}{q-1}$ and from the second $\frac{S(p+1)}{q} \leq d$, so

$$\frac{S(p+1)}{q} \leq d \leq \frac{S(p)}{q-1}.$$

For $k = \frac{q}{p}$, $q \geq 2$, the equation has solutions if and only if there is a natural number between $\frac{S(p+1)}{q}$ and $\frac{S(p)}{q-1}$. If there isn't such a number, then the equation hasn't solutions. However, if there is a number d with $\frac{S(p+1)}{q} \leq d \leq \frac{S(p)}{q-1}$, this doesn't mean that the equation has solutions. This condition is necessary but not sufficient for the equation to have solutions.

For example:

a) $k = \frac{4}{5}$, $q = 4$, $p = 5 \Rightarrow \frac{S(p+1)}{q} = \frac{6}{4} = \frac{3}{2}$, $\frac{S(p)}{q-1} = \frac{5}{3}$. In this case the equation hasn't solutions.

b) $k = \frac{3}{10}$, $q = 3$, $p = 10$; $S(10) = 5$, $\frac{6}{3} = 2 \leq d \leq \frac{5}{2}$. If the equation has solutions, then we must have $d = 2$, $n = dp = 20$, $S(n) = dq = 6$. But $S(20) = 5$.

This is a contradiction. So there are no solutions for $h = \frac{3}{10}$.

We can have more than natural numbers between $\frac{S(p+1)}{q}$ and $\frac{S(p)}{q-1}$. For example:

$$k = \frac{3}{29}, q = 3, p = 29, \frac{S(p+1)}{q} = 10, \frac{S(p)}{q-1} = 14.5.$$

We prove that the equation $\frac{S(n)}{n} = k$ hasn't always solutions.

If $q \geq 2$ then the number of solutions is equal with the number of values of d that verify relation (*). But d can be a nonnegative integer between $\frac{S(p+1)}{q}$ and $\frac{S(p)}{q-1}$, so d can take only a finite set of values. This means that the equation has no solutions or it has only a finite number of solutions.

We study now case $k = \frac{1}{p}$, $p \in \mathbb{N}^*$. In this case the equation has an infinite number of solutions. Let p_0 be a prime number such that $p < p_0$ and $n = pp_0$. We have $S(n) = S(pp_0) = p$, so $S(n) = p_0 \cdot \frac{S(n)}{n} = \frac{p_0}{pp_0} = \frac{1}{p}$, so the equation has an infinite number of solutions.

I will refer now to another problem concerning the ratio $\frac{S(n)}{n}$ "Is there an infinity of natural numbers such that $0 < \left\{ \frac{x}{S(x)} \right\} < \left\{ \frac{S(x)}{x} \right\}$?" from the same journal.

I will prove that the only number x that verifies the inequalities is $x = 9$: $S(9) = 6$, $\frac{S(x)}{x} = \frac{6}{9} = \frac{2}{3}$, $\left\{ \frac{x}{S(x)} \right\} = \left\{ \frac{9}{6} \right\} = \frac{1}{2}$ and $0 < \frac{1}{2} < \frac{2}{3}$, so $x = 9$ verifies $0 < \left\{ \frac{x}{S(x)} \right\} < \left\{ \frac{S(x)}{x} \right\}$.

Let $x = p_1^{\alpha_1} \dots p_n^{\alpha_n}$ be the standard form of x .

$S(x) = \max_{1 \leq k \leq n} S(p_k^{\alpha_k})$. We put $S(x) = S(p^\alpha)$, where p^α is one of $p_1^{\alpha_1} \dots p_n^{\alpha_n}$ such that

$$S(p^\alpha) = \max_{1 \leq k \leq n} S(p_k^{\alpha_k}).$$

$\left\{ \frac{x}{S(x)} \right\}$ can take one of the following values : $\frac{1}{S(x)}$, $\frac{2}{S(x)}$, ... , $\frac{S(x)-1}{S(x)}$ because $0 < \left\{ \frac{x}{S(x)} \right\} < \left\{ \frac{S(x)}{x} \right\}$ (We have $S(x) \leq x$, so $\frac{S(x)}{x} \leq 1$ and $\left\{ \frac{S(x)}{x} \right\} \leq \frac{S(x)}{x}$). This means $\frac{S(x)}{x} \geq \frac{1}{S(x)} \Rightarrow S(p^\alpha)^2 > x \geq p^\alpha$. (2)

But $(\alpha p)! = 1 \cdot 2 \cdot \dots \cdot p(p+1) \dots (2p) \dots (\alpha p)$ is divisible by p^α , so $\alpha p \geq S(p^\alpha)$. From this last inequality and (2) it follows that $\alpha^2 p^2 > p^2$. We have three cases:

I. $\alpha=1$. In this case $S(x)=S(p)=p$, x is divisible by p , so $\frac{x}{p} \in \mathbb{Z}$. This is a contradiction.

There are no solutions for $\alpha=1$.

II. $\alpha=2$. In this case $S(x)=S(p^2)=2p$, because p is a prime number and $(2p)! = 1 \cdot 2 \cdot \dots \cdot p(p-1) \dots (2p)$, so $S(p^2)=2p$.

But $\left\{ \frac{px_1}{2} \right\} \in \left\{ 0, \frac{1}{2} \right\}$. This means $\left\{ \frac{px_1}{2} \right\} = \frac{1}{2} \Rightarrow \frac{1}{2} < \frac{2}{px_1} < 4$; p is a prime number $\Rightarrow p \in \{2,3\}$.

If $p=2$ and $px_1 < 4 \Rightarrow x_1 = 1$, but $x=4$ isn't a solution of the equation: $S(4)=4$ and $\left\{ \frac{4}{4} \right\} = 0$.

If $p=3$ and $px_1 < 4 \Rightarrow x_1 = 1$. so $x=p^2=9$ is a solution of equation.

III. $\alpha=3$. We have $\alpha^2 p^2 > p^\alpha \Leftrightarrow \alpha^2 > p^{\alpha-1}$.

For $\alpha \geq 8$ we prove that we have $p^{\alpha-2} > p^2$, $(\forall) p \in \mathbb{N}^*$, $p \geq 2$.

We prove by induction that $2^{n-1} > (n+1)^2$.

$$2^{n-1} = 2 \cdot 2^{n-2} \geq 2 \cdot n^2 = n^2 + n^2 \geq n^2 + 8n > n^2 + 2n + 1 = (n+1)^2, \text{ because } n \geq 8.$$

We proved that $p^{\alpha-2} \geq 2^{\alpha-1} \geq \alpha^2$, for any $\alpha \geq 8$, $p \in \mathbb{N}^*$, $p \geq 2$.

We have to study the case $\alpha \in \{3,4,5,6,7\}$.

a) $\alpha=3 \Rightarrow p \in \{2,3,5,7\}$, because p is a prime number.

If $p=2$ then $S(x)=S(2^3)=4$. But x is divisible by 8, so $\left\{ \frac{x}{S(x)} \right\} = \left\{ \frac{x}{4} \right\} = 0$, so $x=4$ cannot be a solution of the inequation.

If $p=3 \Rightarrow S(x)=S(3^3)=9$. But x is divisible by 27, so $\left\{ \frac{x}{S(x)} \right\} = \left\{ \frac{x}{9} \right\} = 0$, so $x=9$ cannot

be a solution of the inequation.

If $p=5 \Rightarrow S(x)=S(5^3)=15$; $\left\{ \frac{x}{S(x)} \right\} = \left\{ \frac{S(x)}{x} \right\} = 0$ $x=5^3 \cdot x_1$, $x_1 \in \mathbb{N}^*$, $(5, x_1)=1$.

We have $0 < \left\{ \frac{5^2 \cdot x_1}{3} \right\} < \left\{ \frac{3}{5^2 \cdot x_1} \right\}$. This first inequality implies $\left\{ \frac{5^2 \cdot x_1}{3} \right\} \in \left\{ \frac{1}{3}, \frac{2}{3} \right\}$, so $\frac{1}{3} < \frac{3}{5^2 \cdot x_1} \Rightarrow 5^2 \cdot x_1 < 9$, but this is impossible.

If $p=7 \Rightarrow S(x)=S(7^3)=21, x=7^3 \cdot x_1, (7, x_1)=1, x_1 \in \mathbb{N}^*$.

We have $0 < \left\{ \frac{x}{S(x)} \right\} < \left\{ \frac{S(x)}{x} \right\} \Rightarrow 0 < \left\{ \frac{7^2 \cdot x_1}{3} \right\} < \frac{3}{7^2 \cdot x_1}$. But $0 < \left\{ \frac{7^2 \cdot x_1}{3} \right\}$ implies $\left\{ \frac{7^2 \cdot x_1}{3} \right\} \in \left\{ \frac{1}{3}, \frac{2}{3} \right\}$.

We have $\frac{1}{3} \leq \left\{ \frac{7^2 \cdot x_1}{3} \right\} \Rightarrow 7^2 \cdot x_1 < 9$, but is impossible.

b) $\alpha=4 : 16 \Rightarrow p \in \{2,3\}$.

If $p=2 \Rightarrow S(x)=S(x^2)=6, x=16 \cdot x_1, x_1 \in \mathbb{N}^*, (2, x_1)=1, 0 < \left\{ \frac{x}{S(x)} \right\} < \frac{S(x)}{x} \Rightarrow 0 < \left\{ \frac{8x_1}{3} \right\} < \frac{3}{8x_1}$.

$0 < \left\{ \frac{8x_1}{3} \right\} \Rightarrow x_1=1 \Rightarrow x=16$.

But $\frac{S(x)}{x} = \frac{6}{16} = \frac{3}{8}; \left\{ \frac{x}{S(x)} \right\} = \left\{ \frac{16}{6} \right\} = \left\{ \frac{8}{3} \right\} = \frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{2}{3} > \frac{3}{8}$, so the inequality isn't verified.

If $p=3 \Rightarrow S(x)=S(3^4)=9, x=3^4 \cdot x_1, (3, x_1)=1 \Rightarrow 9|x \Rightarrow \frac{x}{S(x)} = 0$, so the inequality isn't

verified.

For $\alpha=\{5,6,7\}$, the only natural number $p>1$ that verifies the inequality $\alpha^2 > p^{\alpha-2}$ is 2:

$\alpha=5 : 25 > p^3 \Rightarrow p=2$

$\alpha=6 : 36 > p^4 \Rightarrow p=2$

$\alpha=7 : 49 > p$

In every case $x=2^\alpha \cdot x_1, x_1 \in \mathbb{N}^*, (x_1, 2)=1$, and $S(x_1) \leq S(2^\alpha)$.

But $S(2^5)=S(2^6)=S(2^7)=8$, so $S(x)=8$. But x is divisible by 8, so $\left\{ \frac{x}{S(x)} \right\} = 0$ so the

inequality isn't verified because $0 = \left\{ \frac{x}{S(x)} \right\}$. We found that there is only $x=9$ to verify the

inequality $0 < \left\{ \frac{x}{S(x)} \right\} < \left\{ \frac{S(x)}{x} \right\}$

I try to study some diophantine equations proposed in "Smarandache Function Journal".

1) I study the equation $S(mx)=mS(x)$, $m \geq 2$ and x is a natural number.

Let x be a solution of the equation.

We have $S(x)!$ is divisible by x . It is known that among m consecutive numbers, one is divisible by m , so $(S(x)+1)(S(x)+2)\dots(S(x)+m)$ is divisible by (mx) . We know that $S(mx)$ is the smallest natural number such that $S(mx)!$ is divisible by (mx) and this implies $S(mx) \leq S(x)+m$. But $S(mx) = mS(x)$, so $mS(x) \leq S(x)+m \Leftrightarrow mS(x) - S(x) - m + 1 \leq 0 \Leftrightarrow (m-1)(S(x)-1) \leq 1$. We have several cases:

If $m=1$ then the equation becomes $S(x)=S(x)$, so any natural number is a solution of the equation.

If $m=2$, we have $S(x) \in \{1, 2\}$ implies $x \in \{1, 2\}$. We conclude that if $m=1$ then any natural number is a solution of the equation of the equation; if $m=2$ then $x=1$ and $x=2$ are only solution and if $m \geq 3$ the only solution of the equation is $x=1$.

2) Another equation is $S(x^y)=y^x$, x, y are natural numbers.

Let (x,y) be a solution of the equation.

$(yx) != 1 \dots x(x+1) \dots (2x) \dots (yx)$ implies $S(x^y) \leq yx$, so $y^x \leq yx$ because $S(x^y)=y^x$.

But $y \geq 1$, so $y^{x-1} \leq x$.

If $x=1$ then equation becomes $S(1) = y$, so $y=1$, so $x=y=1$ is a solution of the equation.

If $x \geq 2$ then $x \geq 2^{x-1}$. But the only natural numbers that verify this inequality are $x=y=2$:

$x=y=2$ verifies the equation, so $x=y=2$ is a solution of the equation.

For $x \geq 3$ we prove that $x < 2^{x-1}$. We make the proof by induction.

If $x=3$: $3 < 2^{3-1}=4$.

We suppose that $k < 2^{k-1}$ and we prove that $k+1 < 2^k$. We have $2^k = 2 \cdot 2^{k-1} > 2 \cdot k = k+k > k+1$, so the inequality is established and there are no other solutions then $x=y=1$ and $x=y=2$.

3) I will prove that for any m,n natural numbers, if $m > 1$ then the equation $S(x^n)=x^m$ has no solution or it has a finite number of solutions, and for $m=1$ the equation has a infinite number of solutions.

I prove that $S(x^n) \leq nx$. But $x^m = S(x^n)$, so $x^m \leq nx$.

For $m \geq 2$ we have $x^{m-1} \leq n$. If $m=2$ then $x \leq n$, and if $m \geq 3$ then $x \leq \sqrt[m-1]{n}$, so x can take only a finite number of values, so the equation can have only a finite number of solutions or it has no solutions.

We notice that $x=1$ is a solution of the equation for any m,n natural numbers.

If the equation has a solution different of 1, we must have $x^m = S(x^n) \leq x^n$, so $m \leq n$

If $m=n$, the equation becomes $x^m = S(x^n)$, so x^n is a prime number or $x^n = 4$, so $n=1$ and any prime number as well as $x=4$ is a solution of the equation, or $n=2$ and the only solutions are $x=1$ and $x=2$.

For $m=1$ and $n \geq 1$, we prove that the equations $S(x^m) = x$, $x \in \mathbb{N}^*$ has an infinite number of solutions. Let p be a prime number, $p > n$. We prove that (np) is a solution of the equation, that is $S((np)^n) = np$.

$n < p$ and p is a prime number, so n and p are relatively prime numbers.

$n < p$ implies:

$(np)! = 1 \cdot 2 \cdot \dots \cdot n(n+1) \cdot \dots \cdot (2n) \cdot \dots \cdot (pn)$ is divisible by n^n .

$(np)! = 1 \cdot 2 \cdot \dots \cdot p(p+1) \cdot \dots \cdot (2p) \cdot \dots \cdot (pn)$ is divisible by p^n .

But p and n are relatively prime numbers, so $(np)!$ is divisible by $(np)^n$.

If we suppose that $S((np)^n) < np$, then we find that $(np-1)!$ is a divisible by $(np)^n$, so $(np-1)!$ is divisible by p^n (3). But the exponent of p in the standard form of p in the standard form of $(np-1)!$ is:

$$E = \left[\frac{np-1}{p} \right] + \left[\frac{np-1}{p^2} \right] + \dots$$

But $p > n$, so $p^2 > np > np-1$. This implies :

$$\left[\frac{np-1}{p^k} \right] = 0, \text{ for any } k \geq 2. \text{ We have:}$$

$$E = \left[\frac{np-1}{p} \right] = n-1.$$

This means $(np-1)!$ is divisible by p^{n-1} , but isn't divisible by p^n , so this is a contradiction with (3). We proved that $S((np)^n) = np$, so the equation $S(x^n) = x$ has an infinite number of solutions for any natural number n .

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